

Executive summary

OPEN ACCESS MONITOR - DK

Collection, documentation and administration of
Open Access publication costs in Denmark

Open Access Monitor - DK
(OAM-DK)

Results and recommendations

Deff

Danmarks Elektroniske
Fag- og Forskningsbibliotek

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Results

- Although Denmark and its universities are working nationally towards a green OA strategy, OAM-DK data strongly indicate a gold and hybrid OA publishing practice among university researchers.
- For the 2016 publication year, OAM-DK data shows that about 25% (6487 articles) of the nationally realised OA (36%) publications in the Open Access Indicator derive from gold (69%) and hybrid (31%) articles.
- The national share of OA publishing costs that Danish universities pay as article processing charges (APCs) is above 20% of the annual national subscription portfolio of universities, or DKK 160 MM DKK, of which hybrid costs comprise 8% and gold 13%.
- Some participating institutions provide a benchmark against 2015 OAM-DK data that shows an increased number of gold and hybrid publications and a higher expense ratio to OA.
- Using the OAM-DK's economic estimation model, institutions are now capable of monitoring the OA publishing ecology and economy beyond the universities' regular invoice data, even though numbers rely on the uncertainty of actual paid APC prices.
- At present harvesting metadata from third-party data sources via computational identification of OA and APCs is the most efficient and accurate way to use the OAM-DK model.
- A survey initiated by OAM-DK of the universities' central and noncentral economic units shows that there is no existing practice for bookkeeping publication costs, even though some universities have set up specific account strings.
- Current system solutions on the market for monitoring OA costs are in the early stage of development and not fully fledged for implementation, although OpenAPC is the recipient of wide international support and APC metadata from various sources.
- OAM-DK evidence has led to improved OA data currently not recorded at universities, which means aiming for higher OA uptake, possible reductions in license negotiations and informed strategic decision-making at universities regarding their OA objectives.
- An OAM database and analytics application are under development as proof-of-concept and will be further assessed to specify requirements in a consolidation phase after the project ends.

Recommendations

- Compilation and validation of OAM data should be automated as much as possible to strengthen the efficiency, accuracy and quality of the data.
- Strategies for reimbursement of hybrid OA publications based on OAM data should be developed locally where institutions negotiating deals suspect that double dipping occurs.
- Publishers should stipulate requirements for OA metadata as part of negotiating the standard service level agreement because they possess vital information needed from within their systems.
- Further study of how OAM data are interoperable and possibly can be integrated with existing and related system components and services already in use to enhance the research information management data of universities.
- As current OA monitoring is based on an estimation method, ongoing work should be continued to secure adequate, valid management of APC data.
- Ideally, OA monitoring data and system solutions should aim for compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles.
- Quality-assured monitoring and analysis of OA should be a task organised and governed by research libraries on behalf and in interest of the universities as they hold the core competency.
- Working systematically with accessing, selecting, acquiring, securing, adapting, integrating and representing data, however, requires continuous development of new skill sets and existing capabilities in research libraries.
- By actively engaging in communities of practice teaching data analysis, data science, data coding and software skills, universities and research libraries collaboratively should achieve a baseline of skills that allow them to independently create and scale the needed infrastructure of data and system solutions.
- If harmonisation of monitoring OA and other open research contributions is to succeed on an international scale, accessibility and reusability of data collections must be facilitated by open application programming interfaces, file formats and databases accompanying an open monitoring of open research.

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The full OAM-DK report will be available online 21 December 2018

[Read more](#) about the project

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